

radiant

PROJECT

MS15 Conceptual model of the Transformation Avenues DSS

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Lead Beneficiary: JSI

Milestone Description & Contributors

- **Due date:** 31/08/2023
- **Actual submission date:** 01/02/2024
- **Project start date:** September 1st 2021
- **Duration:** 48 months
- **Work package:** WP6
- **Work package leader:** JSI
- **Milestone Title:** Conceptual model of the Transformation Avenues DSS

- **Mean of Verification**

A report on the validity of the conceptual model will be tested and reported.

1. Milestone description

Objective: The main objective of this milestone, "Conceptual Model of the Transformation Avenues DSS", is to confirm and document that the conceptual model has been effectively tested and reported.

Activities performed: To achieve the milestone of developing the Conceptual Model of the Transformation Avenues DSS, we performed the following activities and made specific decisions:

- A structured, **four-tier approach** was developed for the Transformation Avenues DSS (*Figure 1*). Each tier was designed to contribute an important part of the decision support methodology. A collaborative approach was taken in developing the model. We worked with various stakeholders, including experts in agriculture, sustainability, business modelling and the Aurora farms themselves. This collaboration ensured that the model is not only theoretically sound but also based on practical realities and experiences.
 - **Tier 1 - Questionnaire for the Aurora selection:** The focus was on the selection of Aurora farms. We developed and distributed a comprehensive questionnaire to 20 Aurora farms and selected 9 farms based on their responses. The selection criteria included factors such as the pedoclimatic areas, the type of produce, the impact and the type of distribution chain (short, long, farm to consumer, etc.).
 - **Tier 2 - Designing an initial business model with the Lean Canvas:** It started with an online tutorial that served as a preparatory session for the selected Aurora farms, in which we introduced the Lean Canvas model. At this tier, the first drafts of the business models were developed, based on the insights gained from the "One-on-one workshops" with selected Aurora farms.
 - **Tier 3 - Assessment and recommendations for business model optimization:** We held the second individual "One-on-

One Workshops" with the selected Aurora farms to review and refine their initial drafts of a business model. These workshops helped to gather and integrate additional information into the business briefs, using a custom-designed Business Brief template. The incorporation of the sustainability assessment into the business briefs is currently in progress.

- **Tier 4 - Optimized business model:** Currently in progress and aims to finalize and validate the business models. This stage involves the final assessment of each model based on the comments and recommendations from the previous tiers. Decisions are made on the viability of each business model, leading to either the development of a detailed business plan or a revision/end of process of the business idea.

Figure 1: Decision support methodology based on the four-tier approach.

- The developed Decision support methodology and initial conceptual framework were **presented at the third RADIANT General Assembly** in Dundee, Scotland, on September 14, 2023. This

presentation was an opportunity to showcase our progress and receive valuable feedback from a wider audience. Following the presentation, we carefully reviewed and incorporated the feedback received to align the model with the suggestions and insights of the assembly participants.

2. Mean of Verification

Have you provided the Mean of Verification described in the GA?

Yes: The validity of the conceptual model was tested through its practical application in each tier of the methodology. Part of Tier 3 and 4 are still in development.

Tier 1: Questionnaire for Aurora selection

To ensure a robust and fair selection process, we developed a comprehensive online questionnaire that was distributed to all 20 Aurora farms involved in the project on September 26, 2022 (*Figure 2*). This questionnaire was carefully designed to gather essential data on various aspects of each farm that aligned with the core criteria of our project. The selection criteria included a number of key factors, such as the pedoclimatic areas, the type of produce (feed, food or non-food), the potential impact of the farm's operations and the diversity of the value chain (short, long, etc.). These criteria were chosen to ensure a broad representation of different farming practices and business models, so that we obtain a diverse and comprehensive data set for the DSS.

1. Which underutilised crop are you focusing on for this project? Please specify **only one!** *

Enter your answer

2. For your selected underutilised crop, please indicate what is its main use. *

Food

Feed

Non food

3. In what form does the selected underutilised crop come to the consumer? *

Fresh

Processed

4. What is your key farming-related challenge for your selected underutilised crop (e.g. machinery, climate, soil, water, etc.)? Please, describe. *

Enter your answer

5. What is your key market-related challenge for your selected underutilised crop (e.g. access to consumers, low quantity of products, dietary habits, competition, low prices, etc.)? Please, describe. *

Enter your answer

Figure 2: Part of the questionnaire for selecting Aurora farms

After receiving and analyzing the completed questionnaires from the Aurora farms, we conducted a detailed evaluation of each response, carefully measuring them against our predefined criteria. This analysis led to the selection of 9 Aurora farms (*Table 1*), a decision that not only marks the beginning of a comprehensive investigation of their

business models, but also lays the foundation for the subsequent phases of the DSS development. This crucial step ensures that our DSS is built on a foundation of diverse and relevant data, which directly contributing to its effectiveness and real-world applicability. Such a methodological approach underlines the robustness of our model and its suitability for practical scenarios.

Table 1: List of the nine selected Aurora farms for business model development.

Aurora farm	Country	Partner
4	ES	CSIC
12	DE	ILU
13	PT (Terceira Island)	BIOFO
14	PT	FDM
16	ES	Connecta Natura (CONAT)
17	IT	HIW
18	GR	DiKot
19	BG	IAI-Kemapool
20	IT	CRPA

Tier 2: Designing an initial business model with the Lean Canvas

Tier 2 focused on the development of the first drafts of business models for the selected Aurora farms using the Lean Canvas method, a key element of our conceptual model.

- **Online Tutorial Meeting**

We conducted an online tutorial for all selected Aurora farms and project partners on November 9th from 14:00-15:30 CET. This comprehensive session served a dual purpose: it familiarized participants with Lean Canvas as a business modelling tool and

prepared them for the “One-on-one workshops” to develop their business model. The event consisted of a 45-minute presentation of the Lean Canvas, in which a concrete example was used to show how it can be applied in the development of business models. This was followed by another 45 minutes dedicated to active discussion, allowing participants to engage with the material, ask questions and discuss its application in the context of their farms. The session was recorded (Appendix I) to ensure that the information remains accessible for future reference and for those who could not attend live. The attendance of 12 participants reflected a good level of engagement and interest in the business model development process.

Problem / Opportunity 1 Top 3 problems For the planet, society, business Current solutions Competition, substitutability	Solution 3 Top (3) features Key Metrics 7 Monitoring activities and results related to business, SDGs and circular KPIs	Unique Value Proposition 2 Single, clear, compelling message stating why you're different and worth buying	„Unfair“ advantage 4 Can't be easily achieved, nor easily copied Partners and Channels 5 Path to customers Value chain analysis	Customer Segments Target customers (beneficiaries) 1 Early Adopters
Cost Structure 8 CAC, distribution cost Hosting, people, etc.		Revenue Structure 6 Revenue model, lifetime value Revenue, gross margin		

Figure 3: Visual representation of Lean Canvas framework

• **Online “One-on-One Workshops”**

Following the tutorial, we organized individual online workshops with the selected Aurora farms. From the selected list of 9 Aurora farms, 6 were used (AF12, AF13, AF14, AF17, AF18, AF20). Each Aurora farm was guided through the development of its business model using a specially developed Lean Canvas template (Appendix II). These workshops were personalized and allowed for in-depth discussions and specific guidance. We focused on the unique characteristics and challenges of each Aurora farm. These included pedo-climatic conditions, category (food, feed, non-food), crop type and location of the innovation. We also assessed their position on the Technology Readiness Level (TRL) scale, as shown in Figure 4. The workshops were

instrumental in creating the first drafts of the business models. They also provided an opportunity for immediate feedback and iterative refinement of the data and the Lean Canvas template. This practical approach was crucial in turning the theoretical concepts of the Lean Canvas into concrete strategies for each farm. The diverse categories and innovation levels of the Aurora farms are reflected in the summarized overview presented in Figure 4.

AF	CATEGORY	TYPE OF UC	INNOVATION in the DVC	TRL LEVEL
12				
13				
14				
17				
18				
20				

Figure 4: Overview of partial results from the initial business model drafts for selected Aurora farms. The first column classifies the Aurora farms based on their pedoclimatic areas. The colour coding is defined as follows: blue for farms in Atlantic regions, yellow for those in Mediterranean regions, and green for farms in Continental regions.

Tier 3: Assessment and recommendations for business model optimization

Tier 3 played a central role in testing and refining the conceptual model by applying it to the real task of optimizing business models. The focus of this tier was on further detailed analysis and improvement of the initial business model drafts from Tier 2 through a series of tailored

"One-on-One workshops" and incorporate sustainability criterias with DSS (modification of Pathfinder).

- **Online "One-on-One Workshops" for Review and Optimization:**

We organized a series of dedicated online workshops, each focusing on one of the selected Aurora farms. These workshops served as interactive platforms for reviewing the first drafts of the business briefs developed in Tier 2. Our primary objectives were to assess and refine the business models by thoroughly examining the initial drafts, and identifying strengths and areas for improvement. This process involved detailed discussions on each aspect of the business model, as delineated in the Lean Canvas. To develop the second drafts of the business briefs, we collected additional information to enhance and complete them. This included work on specific details that might not have been fully captured in the initial drafts. To facilitate this purpose, we created a custom-designed Business Brief template (*Figure 5*). This template played a crucial role in structuring the information and insights gained from the workshops (Appendix III). It ensured that the second draft of the business briefs was comprehensive, well-organized, and aligned with the project's objectives.

RADIANT BUSINESS BRIEF TEMPLATE

BUSINESS BRIEF TEMPLATE

I. Aurora farm's profile and background data

Name of the organisation	CRPA - CENTRO RICERCHE PRODUZIONI ANIMALI
Aurora Farm No.	20
Contact person	Elena Bortolazzo
Characteristics of the business: legal type, organisation, (experimental lab, startup, family farm, cooperative, consortium, ...)	Research institute (RTD) involved with a cooperative of 12 farms supplying milk, a part of the cooperative producing the cheese Parmigiano Reggiano <u>prodotto di della Montagna (DOP)</u>
Size of Aurora Farm or area of research (ha, crop production volume or potential, ...)	<u>Aurora farm 20 involves 2 farms: Azienda Agricola Strada which has 110 ha dedicated to forage crops; Azienda Agricola Santa Lucia which has about 120 ha dedicated to forage crops. Both farms are part of San Giorgio dairy.</u>
Type of UC and category (food, feed, non-food)	<u>Alfa-bean-and-clover, different-varieties Feed (alfalfa-is-protein-rich---)FEED Alfalfa (main protein crop used for feeding cows) Intercropping forage wheat + peas (increasing forage production as well as good nutritional profile for feeding cows)</u>
Pedoclimatic area	<u>MediterraneanContinental</u>
TRL level	3 (to be revisited) <u>do they have a prototype? What do you mean with prototype. At the end of the project farmers will have new varieties and crops to be used as feed</u>
Other	

II. Scope of the project: the definition of a problem, its background and consequences

Landraces, ecotypes and varieties of alfalfa, and intercropping of peas with cereals (wheat) bean-and-clover, to improve the resilience of crops used as feed in the production of an important Protected Designation of Origin (PDO) value chain of "Parmigiano Reggiano della-prodotto di Montagna" cheese., shows the improvement of the agronomic, physiological and quality traits of the currently cultivated crops to counter the current issues of climate change and satisfying farm and land management needs. Based in lowland and upland areas.

This objective is achieved using a participatory approach involving farmers, SMEs, dairies and other stakeholders.

The problem is that in order to match the criteria of the DOP and to assure the sustainability of the production, the farmers are constrained to:

- Buy the forage, when the local harvest is insufficient due to overexploitation, reduction of pastures and to draughts, etc.), impossible to outweigh within their own facilities in the mountainous area.
- The summer season is increasingly unpredictable due to the volatility of weather conditions for them to harvest the grass in a sequential order and to dry the grass in time.
- Lack of air-drying systems and facilities.

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Figure 5: Partial overview of the Business Brief Template (living document): This figure presents a sample from the second draft of the business brief for Aurora Farm 20.

- **Incorporate Sustainability Criteria** (*in development*)

A key aspect of tier 3 is the integration of the Decision Support System (DSS) with the sustainability criteria outlined in the project. This step is of great importance as it closes any information gaps in the second drafts of the business briefs and ensures that the models not only emphasize economic viability but are also in line with the overall sustainability goals of the project. To achieve this, we will modify the existing sustainability assessment system known as 'Pathfinder' (<https://pathfinder.ijs.si/>), which was originally developed as part of the EU project 'Transition Paths to Sustainable Legume-Based Systems in Europe (TRUE)'. The Pathfinder tool will be adapted to include the specific sustainability assessment criteria identified in our project and will become an integral part of the Decision-Making Toolbox (*Figure 6*). With this Decision-Making Toolbox, we will conduct additional assessments of the selected Aurora farms. The results of these assessments will be seamlessly integrated into the second drafts of the business briefs, which will undergo a final assessment in Tier 4.

Figure 6: Scheme of the decision support methodology framework

Tier 4: Optimized business model

An essential aspect of the tier 4 is the decision-making process regarding the future development of each business model. Based on the final assessment, there are two potential outcomes:

- **Continuation and optimization of the business model:** If a business model is deemed viable and fits well with the project's goals and sustainability criteria, the next step involves formulating detailed comments and recommendations. These recommendations are crucial in achieving the desired outcome and initiating the development of a comprehensive business plan. This plan will outline the strategy for implementation and future development.
- **End of process or revision:** This outcome may be necessary in cases where the business model falls below the required standards or proves to be unsustainable or unfeasible. In such situations, it may be necessary to contemplate a new specific service, product, or innovation, reformulate the previous one, or completely overhaul the idea.

The outcomes of Tier 4 will ensure that only viable and sustainable business models are pursued.

Appendices

Appendix I: Online tutorial video: [Business model development: LEAN CANVAS.](#)

Appendix II: Lean Canvas template

Appendix III: Business Brief template

Appendix II: Lean Canvas template

LEAN CANVAS TEMPLATE

Dear Aurora farm

Below you will find questions to help you complete your Lean Canvas, a ready-made example (from DIKOT: A vegan vanilla bean protein bar), **as well as a blank space to fill in your answers.** As presented in the meeting, first define your specific service/product/innovation, then go step by step through the Lean Canvas following the numbers: 1, 2, 3, etc.

<p>Problem / Opportunity 1</p> <p>Top 3 problems For the planet, society, business</p> <p>Current solutions</p> <p>Competition, substitutability</p>	<p>Solution 3</p> <p>Top (3) features</p>	<p>Unique Value Proposition 2</p> <p>Single, clear, compelling message stating why you're different and worth buying</p>	<p>„Unfair“ advantage</p> <p>Can't be easily achieved, nor easily copied 4</p>	<p>Customer Segments</p> <p>Target customers (beneficiaries) 1</p> <p>Early Adopters</p>
	<p>Key Metrics 7</p> <p>Monitoring activities and results related to business, SDGs and circular KPIs</p>		<p>Partners and Channels 5</p> <p>Path to customers Value chain analysis</p>	
<p>Cost Structure 8</p> <p>CAC, distribution cost Hosting, people, etc.</p>		<p>Revenue Structure 6</p> <p>Revenue model, lifetime value Revenue, gross margin</p>		

Please complete your Lean Canvas case by the one-on-one meeting.
If you need assistance, please contact us at: tanja.dergan@ijs.si

We look forward to working with you!

With kind regards,
JSI and META team

Define your specific service/product/innovation business:

PROBLEM /OPPORTUNITY 1
CURRENT SOLUTIONS

Top 3 problem

Make sure that the problems described are the actual problems. Identify and validate them together with your “customers” (problem/”customer” fit). Being able to solve problems is key to make sure results are used and that the envisaged impact is achieved.

- What is the crucial problem faced by your consumer (the problem your potential users have)?
- Capture their central frustration.

Existing alternatives (Current solutions)

Alternative solutions are important to benchmark the proposed innovation and to get a better insight on competition. Having a picture of the weaknesses and strengths of the alternative solutions, will help you to compare and to quantify the added value of your solution and to have insight on how the alternative solutions are delivered (who is providing them and which conditions).

- Define one clear direct competitor.
- Consider the other ways customers can address their problem (how your “customer” has solved the problem so far).
- What product or service exist as alternatives to what your offering?

Example

Top 3 problem

- Lack of gluten free, nut free and vanilla free bars for allergy sufferers
- Expensive products
- Flooding the market with poor quality and bad taste bars

Existing alternatives (Current solutions)

- Other protein bars based on vegetable proteins
- Make a protein bar at home (Pinterest)

Top 3 problem

-

Existing alternatives (Current solutions)

-

UNIQUE VALUE PROPOSITION 2

A clear and compelling message

Describe in a few lines your result and/or solution (i.e. product, service, innovation, etc.). Your Unique Value Proposition represents why should customers buy your product and not a competitor's product. It also shows where you stand out and why a customer segment should invest time or money in you.

- This should explain what you do?
- How are you different?
- Why are you worth investing in?
- What is your promise to consumers?
- Zero in on the heart of your service and highlight what stands out about product you provide.

High level concept

- How does your product fit into the bigger picture (magnitude of the value that your solution is offering)?
- Where does it fall in the grand scheme of things?
 - ✓ What is the public acceptance?
 - ✓ What is the environmental, economic and social impact?

Example

A clear and compelling message

- Production vegan vanilla bean protein bar
- Use of indigenous bean varieties
- An affordable product for allergy sufferers

High level concept

- Promoting healthy lifestyles
- Improving sustainability through the use of UC

A clear and compelling message

-

High level concept

-

SOLUTION 3

Top 3 solution

What's the answer to your customers' problems that you're going to offer them? You won't always have the perfect solution right away, but the purpose of creating a business plan is to help you get started. If you want to find the solution to your problem, talk to your customer segments to find out what they want and need.

- What is your solution to consumers problems?
- What does your solution do better and how do your solution solve his/her problem better than alternative solutions, what distinguishes you from the competition / current solutions?
- What are the market trends related to your solution?
- Present the defining elements of your service: what makes it the top tool for addressing consumers need?

Example

Top 3 solution

- High protein bars for allergy sufferers, spuds and vegans
- Affordable product (by product)
- Tasty and of high quality with guarantee of origin

Top 3 solution

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UNFAIR ADVANTAGE 4

Your differentiator

The Unfair Advantage is about a specific part of your company, product or service that your competitors can't just get or copy. The specific part, that only you have! This could be exclusive access to data, a community, authority, experience or perhaps a particular feature. Your Unfair Advantage represents why your current and new competitors should NOT try to poach your customers.

- How do you stand out from competitors?
- What puts you ahead of the pack?
- Why should consumer have confidence in your service above others?

Example	<p>Your differentiator</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • An indigenous bean variety that could only be grown in Greece. • Supply of raw material guaranteed from domestic production.
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Your differentiator

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PARTNERS AND CHANNELS 5

Path to consumers

How will you reach your customer segment? In the beginning, it's not important to look at scalability, but at gathering insights. Identify the channels you will use to connect to early adopters. Think whether the chosen channels are suitable for your choice of customers and consider whether they will be enough to establish the needed reputation on the market.

- How do you interact with consumers? Inform them of your developments and services.
- Print ads, social media, platform, promotional events or even word of mouth.
- Consider the most effective ways to reach users.
- If you need to integrate your "team", who do you need as a (new) external partner? What kind of external providers?

Example

Path to consumers

- social networks
- brand
- promotional events
- word of mouth advertising
- collaboration with fitness centers, medical centers

Path to consumers

-

REVENUE STRUCTURE 6

Revenue model, life time value, gross margin, ect.,
 Revenues generate the cash flow that will make the use of the result sustainable over time (at least covers the cost needed to deliver your solution, maintain it, keep it state of the art over time, repay investors and depreciation). Provide an estimation concerning the first month or year. It is recommended that you estimate the revenues according to your early adopters and potential customers.

- What monetary sources will fuel your company?
- How will you generate income? What exactly will you charge and how? (price positioning, loyalty, payment method, payments collection, commercial terms, etc.)
- Present a pricing model for your product or service, and then highlight other sources of revenue ad sales, subscription fees, or asset sales.

Example	<p>Revenue model, life time value, gross margin, ect.,</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • protein vegan bar price online: Life time value of one customer per month: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ 1 week = 3 bars /12 bars per month ✓ 1,59 eur*12=19,08 eur per consumer per month
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Revenue model, life time value, gross margin, ect.,

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KEY METRICS 7

Key activities you measure

Your Lean Canvas should outline how you will measure your performance and success. Key Metrics allow you to track and evaluate the success of your business process. A Key Metric could be daily visitors to your site, the number of company emails opened by consumers per hour or the monthly sales of a specific feature.

- How will you trace consumer engagement, excitement and usage of your product?

Example

Key activities you measure

- refunding returning customers
- promotional events?

Key activities you measure

-

COST STRUCTURE 8

Customer acquisition cost, distribution costs, hosting, people, ect.,

Provide information on the costs and investments needed to bridge the end product/service/innovation to the market. These costs can take many forms: the fixed costs of building rental, the variable costs of hourly wages, the sometimes-unpredictable costs of repairs or disaster response. In other words, the cost structure includes the key resources that your company has to spend to generate revenue.

- What will it cost to launch and maintain your business?
- Consider each stage of your start-up from creating a website and acquiring users, to hiring employees and production goods, to marketing products and getting them to consumers.

Example

Customer acquisition cost, distribution costs, hosting, people, ect.,

- labor
- distribution costs
- inventory
- promotion

Customer acquisition cost, distribution costs, hosting, people, ect.,

-

Appendix III: Business Brief template

BUSINESS BRIEF TEMPLATE

I. Aurora farm's profile and background data

Name of the organisation	
Aurora Farm No.	
Contact person	
Characteristics of the business: legal type, organisation, (experimental lab, startup, family farm, cooperative, consortium, ...)	
Size of Aurora Farm or area of research (ha, crop production volume or potential, ...)	
Type of UC and category (food, feed, non-food)	
Pedoclimatic area	
TRL level	
Other	

II. Scope of the project: the definition of a problem, its background and consequences

What is the problem that a specific Aurora farm is addressing in relation to a specific underutilised crop?

What is the core of a problem? Why does the problem occur?

What underlying circumstances have caused the problem and are the reason for the problem to persist?

What are specific consequences caused by this problem, related to the specific underutilised crop?

III. Industry information

a) General industry information

Type, size, attractiveness and maturity of the relevant industry sector; number of actors (producers), level of vertical integration and their concentration

b) Competitive situation

c) Dynamic value chain situation

IV. Target consumers and target customers

Define and describe target consumers (users)

Define target customer segments

V. Aurora Farm’s objectives and desired outcome(s)

Objectives are specifically related to the problem defined above. Furthermore, they must be me clearly defined, measurable achievable and time constrained.

Objectives must be represented by a short description of a desired outcome for the specific Aurora farm.

VI. Desired approach (business model): ways to get to desired outcome(s)

A short description of the business model being sought or even exercised by the Aurora farm, which aims to resolve the defined problems and to lead to the desired outcomes

What are key alternative solutions?

Enclose a Lean canvas of the Aurora farm’s business model...!

VII. Implementation steps, completion milestones and limitations of each step

Time needed to start the implementation of the business plan and a viable start of the project implementation

How would you subdivide the project implementation into several steps (phases)? What are the milestones for the completion of each of these steps?

Are there any preconditions, limitations or risks related to the completions of each of the milestones? – Please, identify and characterise them...!

VIII. Target available budget

IX. Who?

- a) Team members (responsible for the implementation of key tasks and activities for the project implementation)
- b) Key stakeholders:
 - background actors (stakeholders)
 - side ground actors (stakeholders)

X. Time frame for the resolution of the problem (completion date)

Please, present a Gantt chart of the key steps, milestones and responsibilities of Team members and other involved actors.

XI. Key risks and mitigation

Outline and characterise key risks and explain. how you are going to mitigate each of them.

XII. Supplementary sources

Comments

Comments observe the project sustainability criteria: (1) economic, (2) environmental, (3) health, (4) nutrition.

Recommendations

Recommendations refer to the project.

LEAN CANVAS

AURORA FARM No. _____

INNOVATION IN A VALUE CHAIN:

LEAN CANVAS

Top 3 problem

-
-
-

Existing alternatives (Current solutions)

-
-
-
-

Target consumers

-

Early adopters

-
-

A clear and compelling message

-
-
-

High level concept

-
-

Top 3 solution

-
-
-

Your differentiator

-

Path to consumers

-

Revenue model, life time value, gross margin, etc.,

-

Key activities you measure

-

Customer acquisition cost, distribution costs, hosting, people, etc.,

-
-
-
-

TRL Level:

TECHNOLOGY READINESS LEVELS

